

Effectiveness of Music Therapy on Quality of Sleep among Nursing Students: A Quasi-Experimental Study

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Received: Jan 27, 2026

Accepted: Feb 23, 2026

Published: Feb 24, 2026

Abstract

Background: Aim of the study was to assess the effectiveness of music therapy on the quality of sleep among nursing students.

Method: This Quasi-experimental study was thus conducted on conducted 170 (85 in experimental and 85 in control group) nursing students with the aim to assess the effectiveness of music therapy on the quality of sleep among nursing students. The data was collected on sociodemographic parameters, Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index. Pre-test was conducted using PSQI in both experimental and control group. Music therapy was given to experimental group for the duration of 30 minutes for 30 days whereas no intervention was given to control group. Post-test was conducted on 31st day among both groups.

Result: The findings revealed that post-test PSQI mean scores of students in the experimental group after listening to music were lower than the mean scores of the students in the control group.

Conclusion: As a result of this study, it was determined that music therapy increased the sleep quality of students

Key words: Insomnia, Music Therapy, Quality of Sleep, anxiety.

Introduction

Sleep is essential for physical restoration, cognitive processing, and emotional regulation, in today's hyper connected era, many factors including excessive use of mobile phones, social media engagement, academic pressures, and elevated stress levels disrupt normal sleep wake cycles, contributing to a rising burden of insomnia and poor sleep quality.¹ In the present era one of the most important health problems especially for nurses and nursing students due to shift work is sleep disturbance. Data from studies show that the severity of sleep disorders among nurses is 30.4%.² According to a World Health Organization survey, 27% of the global population suffers from sleep disorders.³ Sleep disorders have a dual negative influence on nurses' physical and mental health, including chronic diseases and negative mental emotions such as depression.⁴

Music is one of the promising non-pharmacological intervention is music-supported therapy (MST) tat significantly improve sleep quality in individuals suffering from insomnia as it facilitates relaxation, promotes physiological regulation, and activates interactions between perceptual and motor systems.⁵ Relaxing music like nature sounds and spending time in

nature can improve the sleep quality and sense of relaxation.⁶ While pharmacological treatments exist, non-pharmacological approaches like music therapy have shown promise in enhancing sleep quality. In a recent metanalysis it was found that that music therapy significantly enhances subjective sleep quality, particularly through subjective perception pathways like emotional regulation and anxiety relief.⁷

Music therapy which are low-cost and free of side effects, have been demonstrated to improve sleep quality and thus has garnered significant interest.⁸ The existing evidences from studies indicates that intervention outcomes of music therapy may vary by participants' age or health conditions, indirectly suggesting potential variations in music intervention efficacy across individuals, age groups, and health conditions.⁷ Thus the present study presented the hypothesis that sleep quality of life nursing students can be improved by music therapy and was carried out with the aim to assess the effectiveness of music therapy on improving the quality of sleep among nursing students.

The primary (I, II and III) and secondary (IV) objectives of the study were as follows;

- To assess the quality of sleep among students in the experimental and control groups by conducting a pre-test.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of music therapy on the quality of sleep among students in the experimental group by conducting a post-test.
- To compare the pre-test and post-test scores of quality of sleep between the experimental and control groups.
- To find out the association between post-test quality of sleep and selected socio-demographic variables among students in the experimental and control groups.

Material and Methods

This quasi-experimental study was conducted on 170 nursing students from the College of Nursing, Adesh University, Bathinda, Punjab after the approval from the research committee and Ethical committee for Biomedical and Health Research of the university. A convenience sampling technique was employed to select the participants, with 85 students assigned to the control group and 85 to the experimental group. The study was explained to the patients, and permissions from participants were sought by informed consent, while confidentiality and anonymity were assured.

The Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) was administered via Google Forms to assess the baseline quality of sleep in both groups (pre-test). The experimental group then received music therapy for 30 minutes daily over a period of 30 days. The intervention was conducted at 10:00 p.m. in a common room were. A link to the music was shared and all participants listened music using headphones. An assistant ensured full participation and adherence during each session. The control group did not receive any intervention. On the thirty-first day, the PSQI was again administered to both groups (post-test) to evaluate changes in sleep quality.

Inclusion Criteria and Exclusion Criteria

The study included only female students from the College of Nursing. Participants were those who expressed their willingness to take part in the study and were available during the period of data collection.

Students who had a history of mental or psychiatric illness, those taking sedatives or medication for sleeping, and those suffering from any medical illness were excluded from the study.

Data analysis

In this research for statistical analysis of data, dependent t-test and independent t-test measures were used. Values of $p < 0.05$ were considered significant. Data were analysed using MS Excel.

Results

Frequency and percentage distribution of socio-demographic variables in experimental group and control group.

Majority 62.4% participants were in the age group of 18-20 years, followed by 20.0% in the age group of 20-22 years in experimental group. In control group, majority 63.5% participants were in the age group of 18-20 years, and 25.9% were in the age group of 20-22 years as. With regard to religion, majority 58.8%, 69.4% participants were Sikh in both experimental and control group. 75.3% from experimental group were from nuclear family where as 55.3% participants in control group were from nuclear family as shown in table 1.

Consider to dietary pattern, 58.8% had mixed dietary pattern followed by 41.2% vegetarian in experimental group where as in control group, 45.8% had mixed dietary pattern and 48.2% were vegetarian. In regard to number of siblings, 2.4% participants had no sibling, 23.6% were having one sibling, in experimental group. In control group, majority 44.7% were having one sibling. In the experimental group 29.4% participants were having more than Rs.30, 000 monthly incomes, and in control group 36.5% had monthly income more than Rs.30, 000. 87.1% participants in experimental group were from B.Sc. Nursing whereas in control group, majority of participants 61.2% were from G.N.M as shown in table 1.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of socio-demographic variables in experimental group and control group (n=170)

Socio demographic variables		Experimental Group		Control Group	
		f	%age	f	%age
Age (in years)	18-20	53	62.4	54	63.5
	20-22	17	20.0	22	25.9
	22-24	12	14.1	5	5.9
	≥24	3	3.5	4	4.7
Religion	Hindu	13	15.3	13	15.3
	Muslim	21	24.7	12	14.1
	Sikh	50	58.8	59	69.4
	Christian	1	1.2	1	1.2
Type of family	Nuclear	64	75.3	47	55.3
	Joint	17	20.0	33	38.8
	Extended	4	4.7	5	5.9
Dietary pattern	Vegetarian	35	41.2	41	48.2
	Mixed	50	58.8	44	51.8
Number of	None	2	2.4	6	7.1
	One	26	30.6	38	44.7

siblings	Two	32	37.6	26	30.6
	More than two	25	29.4	15	17.6
Family monthly income (in rupees)	Less than 10,000	16	18.8	11	12.9
	10,001-20,000	21	24.7	27	31.8
	20,001-30,000	23	27.1	16	18.8
	≥30,000	25	29.4	31	36.5
Course of study	G.N.M	6	7.1	52	61.2
	B.Sc.(N)	74	87.1	33	38.8
	P.B. B.Sc.(N)	0	0.0	0	0.0
	M.Sc.(N)	5	5.9	0	0.0

Findings regarding pre-test and Post test quality of sleep among experimental and control group.

Pre- test: Majority of the participants in the experimental group 55.3% reported poor sleep quality while as 44.7% participants reported good sleep quality. In control group majority of the participants 50.6% reported good sleep quality while as 49.4%) participants reported poor sleep quality as shown in table 2.

Post test: Majority of the participants in the experimental group 63.5% reported good sleep quality while 36.5% participants reported poor sleep quality. In control group majority of the participants 57.6% reported good sleep quality while 42.4% participants reported poor sleep quality as shown in table 2.

Table 2: The pre-test and post test quality of sleep score among the experimental and the control group

Quality of Sleep		Score	Experimental Group		Control Group	
			f	%age	f	%age
Pre-Test (n=170).	Poor Quality	6-21	47	55.3	42	49.4
	Good Quality	0-5	38	44.7	43	50.6
Post-Test (n=170).	Poor Quality	6-21	31	36.5	36	42.4
	Good Quality	0-5	54	63.5	49	57.6

Findings regarding Mean and SD. of pre-test and post-test quality of sleep scores among experimental group and control group.

The mean and Standard Deviation (S.D). of pre-test and post-test quality of sleep score among experimental group was 6.49 ± 3.065 and 5.13 ± 2.618 respectively Where as in the control group the mean and SD of pre-test and post-test quality of sleep score was 6.61 ± 3.140 and 6.25 ± 3.495 respectively as shown in table 3.

Table 3: Mean and SD of pre-test and post-test quality of sleep among experimental group and control group

Group	Pre-test		Post-test	
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
Experimental	6.49	3.065	5.13	2.618
Control	6.61	3.140	6.25	3.495

Findings regarding effectiveness of music therapy on quality of sleep among experimental group.

The pre-test and post-test mean and SD of quality of sleep in experimental group was 6.49 ± 3.065 and 5.13 ± 2.618 respectively. The observed 't' value 3.892 was higher than that of table value 1.98 at degree of freedom (df) 84 and the result was found to be highly significant at 0.05 level of significance. It shows that music therapy was effective in improving the quality of sleep among the nursing students. Hence hypothesis

Pre-test mean and SD of quality of sleep among experimental and control group was 6.49 ± 3.065 and 6.612 ± 3.140 respectively. The pre-interventional calculated 't' value 0.247 was less than that of table value 1.96 at degree of freedom 168 and the result was found to be non-significant at $p < 0.05$ level of significance. Post-test mean and SD of quality of sleep among experimental and control group was 5.13 ± 2.618 and 6.25 ± 3.495 . The post-interventional calculated 't' value 2.360 was higher than that of table value 1.96 at degree of freedom 168 and the result was found to be significant at $p < 0.05$ level of significance.

Table 4: Distribution of pre and post interventional quality of sleep among nursing students in terms of mean and SD in experimental group.

	PSQI Score				Paired t Test			
	Pre-Test		Post-Test		df	t	Table value	p-value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.				
Experimental Group	6.49	3.065	5.13	2.618	84	3.892	1.98	0.001 ^S

Table- 5: The comparison of effectiveness of music therapy on quality of sleep between experimental group and control group.

	Experimental Group		Control Group		Unpaired t-test			
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	df	t-value	Table value	p-value
Pre-test	6.49	3.065	6.612	3.140	168	0.247	1.96	0.805 ^{NS}
Post-test	5.13	2.618	6.25	3.495	168	2.360	1.96	0.019 ^S

Findings regarding association between post-test score of quality of sleep among nursing students in experimental group with their selected socio-demographic variables.

There was no any statistically significant association between age, religion, type of family, dietary pattern, number of siblings, family monthly income course of study with the post-test scores of quality of sleep among nursing students in experimental group at the level of $p < 0.05$ as shown in table 6.

Table 6: Association between post-test score of quality of sleep among nursing students in experimental group with their selected socio-demographic variables.

Demographic variables		Association of PSQI score with demographic variables (Post PSQI) experimental group						
Variables	Options	Poor sleep quality	Good sleep quality	Chi Test	df	Table Value	P Value	Significance
Age (in years)	18-20	20	33	5.463	3	7.815	0.141	NS
	20-22	4	13					
	22-24	7	5					
	≥24	0	3					
Religion	Hindu	3	10	3.974	3	7.815	0.264	NS
	Muslim	6	15					
	Sikh	21	29					
	Christian	1	0					
Type of family	Nuclear	26	38	3.139	2	5.991	0.208	NS
	Joint	5	12					
	Extended	0	4					
Dietary pattern	Vegetarian	12	23	0.123	1	3.841	0.726	NS
	Mixed	19	31					
Number of siblings	None	2	0	5.454	3	7.815	0.141	NS
	One	7	19					
	Two	14	18					
	More than two	8	17					
Family monthly income (in rupees)	≤10,000	6	10	0.062	3	7.815	0.996	NS
	10,001-20,000	8	13					
	20,001-30,000	8	15					
	≥30,000	9	16					
Course of study	G.N.M	2	4	0.052	2	5.991	0.974	NS
	B.Sc.(N)	27	47					
	P.B. B.Sc.(N)	0	0					
	M.Sc.(N)	2	3					

Findings regarding association Findings regarding association between post-test score of quality of sleep among nursing students in control group with their selected socio-demographic variables.

There was statistically significant association between age, religion, course of study and post test score of quality of sleep among nursing students in control group at the level of $p < 0.05$.

Table 7: Association between post-test score of quality of sleep among nursing students in control group with their selected socio-demographic variables.

Demographic Variables		Association of PSQI score with demographic variables (post PSQI) control group						
Variables	Opts	Poor sleep quality	Good sleep quality	Chi Test	df	Table Value	P Value	Significance
Age (in years)	18-20	16	38	13.025	3	7.815	0.005	S
	20-22	16	6					
	22-24	3	2					
	≥24	1	3					
Religion	Hindu	7	6	8.404	3	7.815	0.038	S
	Muslim	9	3					
	Sikh	20	39					
	Christian	0	1					
Type of family	Nuclear	21	26	0.234	2	5.991	0.890	NS
	Joint	13	20					
	Extended	2	3					
Dietary pattern	Vegetarian	13	28	3.676	1	3.841	0.055	NS
	Mixed	23	21					
Number of siblings	None	2	4	13.064	3	7.815	0.004	S
	One	10	28					
	Two	12	14					
	More than two	12	3					
Family monthly income (in rupees)	≤10,000	3	8	1.186	3	7.815	0.756	NS
	10,001-20,000	12	15					
	20,001-30,000	7	9					
	≥30,000	14	17					
Course of study	G.N.M	15	37	10.008	1	3.841	0.002	S
	B.Sc.(N)	21	12					
	P.B. B.Sc.(N)	0	0					
	M.Sc.(N)	0	0					

Discussion

The present study examined the effectiveness of music therapy on sleep quality among nursing students and compared outcomes between experimental and control groups. The findings demonstrate that sleep disturbances were prevalent among students prior to intervention and that music therapy significantly improved sleep quality.

Baseline assessment revealed that more than half of the students in the experimental group and nearly half in the control group reported poor sleep quality during the pre-test phase. This highlights sleep disturbance as a common issue among nursing students, likely related to academic stress, clinical responsibilities, and irregular schedules. These findings are consistent with previous research conducted among college students in India, which reported a high prevalence of poor sleep quality.⁹

Post-intervention analysis showed a statistically significant improvement in sleep quality among students in the experimental group who received music therapy. The mean sleep quality score decreased from 6.49 ± 3.065 to 5.13 ± 2.618 , indicating better sleep following the intervention ($p < 0.05$). This confirms the effectiveness of music therapy on quality of sleep. Similar outcomes have been reported in studies assessing the impact of music therapy on students' sleep, suggesting that music promotes relaxation and reduces psychological arousal, thereby enhancing sleep quality.¹⁰

Further comparison between experimental and control groups demonstrated that while the experimental group showed notable improvement, the control group exhibited minimal change in sleep quality scores. These findings are consistent with earlier experimental studies among nursing students, where music therapy significantly improved sleep quality compared to controls.¹¹

Analysis of socio-demographic variables revealed no significant association between post-test sleep quality and selected variables in the experimental group, indicating that music therapy was effective across demographic categories. In contrast, certain demographic factors were significantly associated with sleep quality in the control group. These results are in agreement with previous studies reporting minimal demographic influence on sleep outcomes following music therapy interventions.¹¹

Overall, the findings suggest that music therapy is a cost-effective, non-invasive, and feasible intervention for improving sleep quality among nursing students.

Conclusion

To conclude that quality of sleep/insomnia affects all the age groups whether it is children, young adults or old aged. As evidenced, prevalence of insomnia rate is increasing day-by-day, affecting all the population groups including young adults also. Particularly those within nursing profession are under a great deal of insomnia because of intense workload and professional training.

This study set out to investigate the impact of music therapy on quality of sleep. A quantitative research approach was chosen for the current investigation. A quasi-experimental two-group pre-test-post-test design with control was the research design employed for the investigation. The 170 nursing students from Adesh University's College of Nursing in

Bathinda, Punjab, were chosen using the convenience sampling technique. The PSQI was used to gather data, statistical technique was applied for additional analysis and interpretation. Students who receive music therapy sleep better, are more comfortable, and feel more at ease. Since music therapy is a non-pharmacological and effective way to improve quality of sleep, nurse educators should be knowledgeable about it. Nursing staff and students should receive sufficient hands-on training in music therapy so they may apply it in clinical and community settings as well as on themselves.

Recommendations for further study

The following suggestions have been made in light of the study's outcomes:

1. The results could be generalised from a comparable study with a bigger sample size.
2. Patients with illnesses can be the subject of a similar investigation.

Limitations

The research was restricted to:

1. Sample size of present study was limited to 170 nursing students.
2. The Study was confined to students of College of Nursing, Adesh University, Bathinda, Punjab.
3. Researcher cannot control other factors that can affect the quality of sleep in students such as support system, social culture.

References:

1. Yan, Di, et al. "Bedtime Music Therapy for College Students with Insomnia: A Randomized Assessor-Blinded Controlled Trial." *Sleep Medicine*, vol. 121, Sept. 2024, pp. 326–335, doi:10.1016/j.sleep.2024.07.018.
2. Wang, Xia, et al. "Application of Music Therapy in Improving the Sleep Quality and Mental Health of Nurses with Circadian Rhythm Sleep Disorders Caused by Work Shifts." *Noise & Health*, vol. 26, no. 122, 2024, pp. 294–299, doi:10.4103/nah.nah_32_24.
3. Zhou, Lin, et al. "Sex Differences in the Effects of Sleep Disorders on Cognitive Dysfunction." *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, vol. 146, 2023, article 105067, doi:10.1016/j.neubiorev.2023.105067.
4. Zhang, Hui, et al. "Relationship between Night Shift and Sleep Problems, Risk of Metabolic Abnormalities of Nurses: A Two-Year Follow-Up Retrospective Analysis in the National Nurse Health Study (NNHS)." *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health*, vol. 96, 2023, pp. 1361–1371, doi:10.1007/s00420-023-02014-2.
5. Ding, Jing, et al. "Effectiveness and Safety of Music Therapy for Insomnia Disorder Patients: A Protocol for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis." *Medicine*, vol. 100, no. 26, 2021, article e26399, <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8257833/>.
6. Hosseini, Neda, et al. "The Effect of Music Therapy on the Sleep Quality of Patients with Heart Failure: The Miracle of Nature Music." *Iranian Journal of Nursing and Midwifery Research*, vol. 29, no. 4, 2024, pp. 424–430, doi:10.4103/ijnmr.ijnmr_385_22.
7. Gou, Qiaoqiao, et al. "Meta-Narrative Review: The Impact of Music Therapy on Sleep and Future Research Directions." *Frontiers in Neurology*, vol. 15, 2025, article 1433592, doi:10.3389/fneur.2024.1433592.

8. Tang, Hui, et al. “The Efficacy of Music Therapy to Relieve Pain, Anxiety, and Promote Sleep Quality in Patients with Small Cell Lung Cancer Receiving Platinum-Based Chemotherapy.” *Supportive Care in Cancer*, vol. 29, 2021, pp. 7299–7306, doi:10.1007/s00520-021-06152-6.
9. Kumari, Renu, et al. “Sleep Quality Assessment among College Students Using Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index in a Municipal Corporation Area of Uttarakhand, India.” *The Ceylon Medical Journal*, vol. 65, no. 4, 2020, pp. 86–94, doi:10.4038/cmj.v65i4.9279.
10. Lin, Dan. “Effects of Music Therapy on Sleeping for High School Students.” *Lecture Notes in Education Psychology and Public Media*, vol. 6, 2023, pp. 419–424, <https://www.ewadirect.com/proceedings/lnep/article/view/1514>.
11. Kavurmacı, Melek, Nurcan Dayapoğlu, and Mustafa Tan. “Effect of Music Therapy on Sleep Quality.” *Alternative Therapies in Health and Medicine*, vol. 26, no. 4, 2020, pp. 22–26, <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31221932/>.

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